

NORDIC
COMPUTATIONAL BIOLOGY

NORDIC COMPBIO WEEK 2025

ESTONIA + FINLAND

23-24 OCTOBER 2025
TALLINN UNIVERSITY, ESTONIA

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MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF CARDIAC MUSCLE COOPERATIVITY WITH CROSS-BRIDGE ENSEMBLES

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Recent advances in muscle physiology have highlighted the importance of cooperativity between neighboring cross-bridges in describing the actomyosin dynamics. We incorporate cooperativity into a modified Huxley-type model. The cross-bridges are divided into ensembles and each cross-bridge is influenced by its neighbors. The model also ensures thermodynamic consistency, such that the produced mechanical force is linked to the free energy of the system.

In the model, cooperativity is induced by the deformation of tropomyosin. The binding of calcium or a cross-bridge leads to the displacement of tropomyosin, which in turn influences the free energy of the cross-bridge group. Simulations are made on infinitely long strings consisting of cross-bridges/RUs that interact via closest neighbor interaction. The model tracks only one cross-bridge, assuming that the neighboring cross-bridges have the same distribution between their states.

Our current study aims to enhance the model's fit to isometric stress data across various sarcomere lengths. To achieve this, we refined the calcium function for improved representation of calcium transients. We optimized model parameters by fitting to the linear relation between oxygen consumption and stress-strain area, and stress dynamics of rat trabecula. Through the simulations, we have found parameter sets for each sarcomere length and derived the relationships between their rate constants describing binding of cross-bridges and interaction with tropomyosin. Our findings reveal a relationship between sarcomere length and cross-bridge kinetics that may contribute to our understanding of length-dependent activation in cardiac muscle.

ISOFORM-SPECIFIC MAPPING OF RNA BINDING PROTEIN SITES USING NANOPORE LONG-READ SEQUENCING

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RNA binding proteins (RBPs) are key regulators of post-transcriptional gene expression, influencing RNA splicing, stability, and translation. Traditional methods such as UV crosslinking and immunoprecipitation followed by short-read sequencing (CLIP-seq) have been widely used to identify RBP binding sites. However, these approaches face limitations in resolving isoform-specific binding due to short read lengths and PCR amplification artifacts.

To overcome these limitations, we developed both the experimental protocols and bioinformatics pipelines that combine CLIP with Oxford Nanopore Technologies long-read direct cDNA sequencing (dirCLIP), enabling isoform-specific RBP binding site mapping without PCR amplification. Upon UV treatment, RBPs are covalently crosslinked to RNA. Proteinase K digestion leaves a residual amino acid at the crosslink site, which induces mutations or deletions during reverse transcription. Nanopore sequencing captures full-length cDNA reads, enabling the detection of these mutation sites across complete RNA isoforms.

Using a custom computational workflow, we uniquely assigned reads to specific isoforms and identified statistically significant mutation sites indicative of RBP binding. Benchmarking dirCLIP with SRSF3 demonstrated >75% concordance with iCLIP motifs and revealed binding to predominantly single isoforms. Application to a noncanonical RBP HMGA1 isoforms uncovered AT-hook mediated RNA interactions.

This integrated experimental-computational framework enables isoform-specific identification of RBP binding sites, offering new insights into RNA-protein interactions and expanding the utility of long-read sequencing technologies in transcriptomic research.

BEYOND FCS: BAYESIAN SINGLE-MOLECULE ANALYSIS WITH FITSA

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Molecular movement and interactions at the single-molecule level in live cells are often studied using fluorescence correlation spectroscopy (FCS). However, FCS analysis typically assumes independence of residuals when fitting the autocorrelation function (ACF), which can lead to overfitting. The field has limited tools to address this, with conventional solutions requiring impractically long experiments. Non-parametric Bayesian methods for direct analysis of fluorescence intensity traces have been proposed, but face computational expense and adoption barriers. To address these issues, we introduce Fluorescence Intensity Trace Statistical Analysis (FITSA), a novel Bayesian method that improves robustness and efficiency. FITSA directly analyzes fluorescence intensity traces by splitting them into smaller sections, each representing a single fluorescent particle passage, with strategic particle seeding. These improvements enable faster convergence, more robust parameter estimation, and analysis of longer traces. Comparing FITSA and FCS using synthetic and experimental data, we found FITSA achieves comparable precision while requiring 2-11× fewer photons. When accounting for photons needed to correct ACF point interdependence, FITSA becomes 300-21,000× more efficient than FCS. In conclusion, FITSA enables estimation of diffusion coefficients and other parameters from short fluorescence intensity traces, offering an attractive alternative for studying molecular events in experiments currently employing FCS.

ENDOTHELIAL CELL SUBPOPULATIONS IN ENDOMETRIOSIS- AND ADENOMYOSIS-ASSOCIATED VASCULARIZATION

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OBJECTIVE: : To study the cellular and molecular mechanisms underlying endometriosis and adenomyosis by integrating single-cell transcriptomic data and genome-wide association study (GWAS) findings into a comprehensive single-cell atlas.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: To gain a more comprehensive understanding of the etiology of these diseases, we have integrated the available single-cell transcriptomic data from eutopic endometrium, all endometriosis subtypes and adenomyosis into an extensive single-cell atlas of more than 700,000 cells.

RESULTS: We observed that several endometriosis GWAS-detected genes are abundantly expressed in endothelial cells. Additionally, we observed that in the endometrium of endometriosis patients compared to controls, there are more cells in two specific endothelial subpopulations. These populations were annotated as endothelial microvascular capillary cells and lymphatic endothelial cells. Several endothelial subpopulations also had increased expression of estrogen receptor 2 (ESR2) and hypoxia inducible factors (HIFs). We will further analyze the endothelial subpopulations with trajectory, cell-to-cell communication and gene regularoty network analysis and aim to validate the main findings in patient derived tissue sections.

CONCLUSIONS: Our integrative single-cell analysis reveal an important role of endothelial cells in these conditions. The analysis shows a possibility of endothelia-specific cross-talk of hormonal and hypoxia signaling.

IMPACT STATEMENT: Detailed analysis of endothelial cell populations may provide new drug targets associated with vascular interactions in endometriosis and adenomyosis.

ENHANCING REPRODUCIBILITY IN MICROBIOME DIFFERENTIAL ABUNDANCE ANALYSIS

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The proliferation of methods for microbiome differential abundance analysis (DAA) has contributed to a reproducibility crisis, as methodological variability often yields conflicting biological conclusions. Large-scale benchmarking studies highlight this problem, showing that complex, normalization-dependent techniques frequently produce inconsistent results. In contrast, these same studies identify elementary methods-such as Wilcoxon rank-sum tests on relative abundances and logistic regression on presence/absence data-as among the most reproducible. Despite this, there is currently no dedicated package that provides an accessible, standardized, and interpretable implementation of these elementary DAA methods. To translate this evidence into practice, we present an R package `daa` that standardizes the implementation of these robust, elementary methods. The package is being developed in the Bioconductor ecosystem-an open-source, collaborative project providing R packages and tools for the analysis of high-throughput genomic and biological data-, integrating seamlessly with standard data structures (`TreeSummarizedExperiment`) and interoperating with other core Bioconductor packages for microbiome analysis. It provides a streamlined toolkit for non-parametric tests, regression models and intuitive result visualization, prioritizing transparency and empirical performance over algorithmic novelty. The ongoing effort offers a principled alternative to complex DAA methods, strengthening reproducibility and interpretability in microbiome research through evidence-based, standardized analysis workflows.

Keywords: differential abundance, reproducibility, R package, microbiome, Bioconductor

EXPLORING THE ESTONIAN GUT MICROBIOTA: COMPOSITION, STRUCTURE, AND RESEARCH POTENTIAL

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Background: Understanding how the human gut microbiota varies across populations and life stages is essential, given its links to health and diet. However, region-specific data, such as from Estonia, remain limited.

Study question: What is the taxonomic composition and enterotype structure of the Estonian gut microbiota, and how can microbiota profiling support dietary intervention research?

Methods: Approximately 1,800 Estonian gut microbiota samples were collected and characterized by 16S rRNA sequencing, alongside anthropometric, dietary, and disease related metadata. Community structure was assessed via principal coordinate analysis, hierarchical clustering, and diversity metrics to describe the community structure. Differential abundance analysis and multivariate methods were used to detect enterotype specific patterns and their associations with metadata variables. As a case study, a three-week intervention involving daily consumption of fermented vegetables was conducted in a subset of participants to illustrate how gut microbiota profiling can support nutritional studies and inform evidence-based conclusions.

Main results: Our analysis revealed the most dominant bacterial genera in the Estonian population and identified distinct enterotypes that may serve as a foundation for future studies on disease and dietary associations. Dietary intervention showed that consumption of fermented vegetables increased the abundance of butyrate-producing and anti-inflammatory bacterial species. Improvements in phase angle suggest enhanced metabolic health.

Limitations: 16S rRNA sequencing provides limited functional and strain-level resolution compared to shotgun metagenomics. Self-reported metadata might introduce potential bias.

Wider implications: Our large-scale characterization of the Estonian gut microbiota provides a foundation for future research and highlights how microbiota profiling can guide evidence-based dietary and health strategies.

GENETIC ARCHITECTURE OF RECURRENT VAGINITIS HIGHLIGHTS THE ROLE OF EPITHELIAL INTEGRITY AND HOST–MICROBIOME INTERACTIONS

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Recurrent vaginitis, encompassing bacterial vaginosis and vulvovaginal candidiasis, is among the most frequent gynecological conditions worldwide. Its recurrent nature and multifactorial etiology remain poorly understood. To uncover host genetic determinants, we conducted a genome-wide association study (GWAS) using genotypic and clinical data from the Estonian Biobank. Both single-marker and gene-based analyses were performed, followed by functional annotation and pathway enrichment of associated loci. A genome-wide significant association was identified for KRT6A, a keratin family gene expressed in differentiating epithelial tissues. Comparative analysis with prior candidate gene studies further supported roles for LBP and PRKCH, genes implicated in innate immune signaling and epithelial barrier function. These findings collectively point to the critical contribution of the vaginal epithelium in defense against microbial imbalance and recurrent infection. Although the vaginal lining is histologically non-keratinized, it relies on keratin proteins to maintain mechanical resilience and epithelial integrity, potentially influencing susceptibility to recurrent vaginitis.

This study provides the first genome-wide evidence implicating epithelial structure-related genes in recurrent vaginitis. Integration of host genomic and microbiome data offers promising avenues for precision diagnostics and personalized prevention strategies for women prone to recurrent vaginal infections.

REPRODUCTIVE TRACT MICROBIOTA COMPOSITION OF BOTH PARTNERS ASSOCIATES WITH ASSISTED REPRODUCTION OUTCOME

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Despite advances in assisted reproductive technologies (ART), embryo implantation rates remain modest, and the causes of implantation failure often remain elusive. Mounting evidence suggests that microbial communities in the reproductive tract play a critical role in reproductive success. This study explored the relationship between vaginal and seminal microbiota profiles and ART outcomes among couples undergoing ART and fertile control couples. Bacterial communities were characterized using 16S rRNA gene sequencing and bioinformatics clustering of community types. The semen microbiota was found to be more diverse but contained fewer bacterial cells than the vaginal microbiota. In ART patients, vaginal Firmicutes were reduced while Actinobacteria were increased compared to fertile controls. Community typing revealed that women with *Lactobacillus crispatus*-dominated or lactic-acid-bacteria-rich vaginal microbiota achieved higher ART success rates, while those dominated by *L. iners*, *L. gasseri*, or bacterial vaginosis-type communities had poorer outcomes. In men, seminal microbiota dominated by *Acinetobacter* species were associated with the most favorable ART outcomes. Couples in which both partners had beneficial microbial profiles achieved significantly higher pregnancy rates than those with non-optimal microbiota compositions.

Our findings highlight that microbiome balance in both partners may substantially influence ART success and suggest that reproductive tract microbial profiling could serve as a valuable addition to infertility diagnostics and pre-ART evaluation strategies.

IMMUNOMODULATORY EFFECTS OF COCONUT AND GINGER-INFUSED DARK CHOCOLATE EXTRACTS ON RAW264.7 MACROPHAGES

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This study evaluated the immunomodulatory effects of two dark chocolate formulations; dark chocolate (with 70% cocoa ingredients) infused with ginger (GB) and dark chocolate (with 60% cocoa ingredients) infused with coconut (CB) on RAW264.7 murine macrophages, focusing on cell viability, proliferation, nitric oxide (NO) production, phagocytic activity, and cytokine expression. The extractions of both dark chocolates for the above assays performed according to standard procedures. Both extracts were found to be non-cytotoxic up to 50 µg/µL, with MTT assays revealing significantly enhanced cell viability (CB: 165.6 ± 5.6%; GB: 170.4 ± 3.5%; $p < 0.0001$) compared to untreated controls. AlamarBlue assays further confirmed a robust increase in proliferation at 24 h for both CB (170.8 ± 3.7%) and GB (165.1 ± 5.2%), with GB showing a delayed but sustained proliferative effect at 72 h (117.0 ± 7.4%; $p < 0.01$). Anti-inflammatory profiling showed moderate elevation in NO production by both extracts (CB: 6.36 ± 0.18 µM; GB: 4.50 ± 0.12 µM), remaining lower than reported LPS-induced levels, suggesting partial NO modulation. Phagocytic activity, assessed via neutral red uptake, was significantly enhanced in both CB (127.1 ± 5.8%) and GB (132.6 ± 5.1%) treated cells, with GB showing slightly greater stimulation than the positive control (LPS: 116.9 ± 0.9%). Gene expression analysis via qPCR revealed that TNF-α was markedly upregulated in both GB and CB treatments, with CB inducing a more pronounced effect. In contrast, TGF-β expression remained unchanged, indicating selective pro-inflammatory activation without suppression of regulatory cytokine signaling. Light microscopy images confirmed normal cell morphology across treatments, indicating non-cytotoxicity. Both coconut and ginger-infused dark chocolate extracts enhanced macrophage activity and TNF-α expression, highlighting their potential as natural immunomodulatory agents.

STRUCTURE-DEPENDENT BIOACTIVITY OF FUCOIDANS FROM FIVE BROWN SEAWEEDS: IMPLICATIONS FOR WOUND HEALING AND SKIN PROTECTION

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The search for effective wound healing agents remains a significant challenge. Fucoidans, sulfated polysaccharides from brown seaweeds, exhibit therapeutic potential; however, their bioactivity strongly depends on source-specific structural characteristics. A systematic comparison is therefore essential to link structure to function and identify optimal candidates. Fucoidans were extracted from five commercially relevant brown seaweeds—*F. serratus*, *L. hyperborea*, *C. okamuranus*, *A. esculenta*, and *M. pyrifera*—and thoroughly characterized. Their bioactivities were assessed through a comprehensive suite of in vitro assays using RAW264.7 macrophages, human dermal fibroblasts (HDF), and HaCaT keratinocytes. Functional evaluations included immunomodulation (phagocytosis, nitric oxide production), wound healing (proliferation, migration), cytoprotection (LDH assay after UV-B exposure), and cellular metabolism (LC-MS profiling). Results revealed distinct structure–function relationships. *M. pyrifera* fucoidan (F5B, 75 kDa) showed strong anticoagulant activity ($20.0 \pm 0.5\%$ heparin equivalent) and significantly enhanced macrophage proliferation ($187 \pm 2.7\%$, $p < 0.01$) and phagocytosis, while providing potent cytoprotection by reducing UV-B–induced LDH release ($76.1 \pm 5.5\%$, $p = 0.0032$). In contrast, *A. esculenta* fucoidan (F4A) most effectively stimulated HDF proliferation ($128 \pm 7.7\%$, $p < 0.05$) and migration, upregulating key wound-healing genes (TGF- β 1, collagen I). *C. okamuranus* fucoidan (F3B) selectively enhanced phagocytosis ($131.5 \pm 1.6\%$, $p < 0.0001$). LC-MS analysis indicated increased intracellular sugar metabolites following fucoidan treatment, suggesting enhanced cellular metabolism to support proliferation and survival. We propose low-molecular weight *M. pyrifera* fucoidan for immunomodulation and UV protection, and *A. esculenta* fucoidan for tissue repair. These findings establish a foundation for the rational design of advanced fucoidan-based wound healing and skin protection therapies.